

EFFECT OF INDUCED MOLTING ON FERTILITY AND HATCHABILITY CHICKENS

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ABSTRACT

The study was carried out at Da-Ogboe Farms Nigeria Limited, Heipang, Plateau State, between January 2008 and October 2009 to assess the effect of induced or forced molting as a means of improving declined egg production, fertility and hatchability in domestic chicken. In all, 103 sets of incubation were conducted. Significantly ($P < 0.001$) more eggs were set for incubation during the first period of production (pre-molt) than hatchability also differed between the two periods in favor of the first ($71.08 \pm 1.25\%$ and $57.55 \pm 1.02\%$, respectively). Significant seasonal variations were also detected for all fertility and hatchability variables. The highest fertility on day 10 ($91.80 \pm 0.36\%$) and day 18 ($89.80 \pm 0.39\%$) of incubation were observed in early wet season, followed closely by late dry season ($90.70 \pm 0.51\%$ and $88.73 \pm 0.61\%$, respectively). In terms of hatchability per number set on day 1, late dry season recorded the best performance ($73.15 \pm 1.32\%$) ahead of the early wet season ($68.60 \pm 1.98\%$) as well as the other seasons. The study has shown that though egg production, fertility and hatchability in a force-molted flock were lower compared with the active laying period, it is worth practicing in order to get few more eggs out of the exhausted hens, when it is deemed cheaper to recycle them rather than immediately slaughter them after a year of relentless egg-laying.

KEYWORDS : chicken ,egg, fertility, forced- molting, hatchability

INTRODUCTION

The initiation of seasonal feather molting in wild avian species frequently coincides with incubation of eggs and brooding of offspring. A period of natural in-appetence or anorexia usually accompanies this molt. This is particular of the jungle fowl, the wild ancestor of the domestic chicken. Brooding of eggs by the domestic fowl is accompanied by spontaneous anorexia, with little food or water consumed throughout the period of egg production. During this time, the reproductive tract regresses, and feather molting is initiated. Selective breeding for high egg production has blunted the response of the commercial laying hen to exogenous environmental cues and reduced or eliminated the endogenous biological cues that coordinate the initiation of seasonal molting. However, commercial layers retain in their physiological repertoire, the ability to tolerate prolonged fasting and to undergo spontaneous regression of the reproductive tract and feather molting. Induction of a coordinated molt, by manipulation of environmental and nutritional cues, or endocrine manipulation can be used in domestic hen to regenerate and regress the reproductive tract. This improves subsequent egg production and egg shell quality. This process also induces temporary recrudescence of lymphoid tissues and may alter immune function in hens. (Berry, 2003). Reports on the effect of force molting on fertility and hatchability of domestic chickens are very limited. (personal observation). The present study was therefore conducted in an effort to revive the egg production of breeder hens that had declined to less than half of the average production level coupled with reduced fertility and hatchability, using force molting by means of feed restriction.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experiment was carried out at Da-Ogboe Farms Nigeria Limited, Heipang, Plateau State from January 2008 to October 2009. Heipang is in Barkin Ladi Local Government area of Plateau State and is located 26 km away from Jos, the state capital. The state lies between longitude $8^{\circ} 22'$ and $10^{\circ} 38'$ E and latitude $8^{\circ} 22'$ and $10^{\circ} 24'$ N. The highland zone, the geographic plateau, is between longitude $8^{\circ} 51'$ and $9^{\circ} 54'$ E and latitude $9^{\circ} 30'$ and $10^{\circ} 18'$ N and at an altitude of about 1829 metres above sea level (Clarke *et al.*, 1975). Jos experiences an annual rainfall of 1250-2500 mm. Its minimum and maximum daily temperatures averaged 17° C and 28.6° C, respectively, with a mean relative humidity of between 14% and 74% in the dry season, though it could be higher in the rainy season (Barbour *et al.*, 1982). There is a distinctive dry and wet season with rainfall sometimes recorded between January and March but rainfall usually commences in April or May and lasts till October with August as the peak.

A total number of 1,666 hens and 167 cockerels of the Dominant Black 109 breed formed the parent stock observed in the study. The first period of production lasted from January, reached a peak in May and fell well below 50% in December 2008. The process of forced molting using feed restriction lasted for three months (January to March 2009) followed by a second production period of 8 months (March to October 2009). During the latter period, maximum production was attained at the end of the fourth month, persisted for a month and gradually declined to a point of cessation two months later. In all, 103 sets of incubation were conducted (52 before molting and 51 after).

Prior to molting the birds were fed a breeder mash which contained maize, groundnut cake, wheat offal, fish meal, palm kernel cake, limestone, periwinkle, bone meal, premix, toxynil, enzymes, lysine, methionine and salt. Water was provided ad libitum

At the beginning of force molting when the birds were 74 weeks old, all males were separated from the females and deprived of feed and water for the first three days. Water was given on the day 4th day. Beginning from the 5th day, the birds were given a molting ration (4 kg per 100 birds) which consisted mainly of cracked maize and wheat offal with the necessary essential amino acids, salt and premix until the 8th day. The restriction of feed and water was accompanied by an abrupt reduction in lighting of the flock from about 14 h to as low as 6 h for 6 weeks. This combination resulted in heavy molting in most of the hens. Afterwards, normal breeder diet was introduced in combination with the molting ration in the ratio 60:40.

Egg dropping started on day 21 of molting, while normal feeding with breeder ration commenced on day 37. Males were re-introduced to females at day 70, while egg collection for incubation started at day 90.

During incubation a temperature of about 99.5 – 100.2° F and relative humidity of 51 – 52% were maintained in the setter, while a temperature of 99.5 – 100.2° F and relative humidity of 61 – 62% were maintained in the hatcher.

On day 10 of incubation candling was performed using a candler to examine the fertility and internal quality of the eggs. The process was repeated on the 18th day, to remove those that were dead or infertile. The fertile eggs were then transferred into a basket and moved into the hatching machine.

At the end of the 21st day, chicks began to hatch out. The eggs that were not hatched, were sorted into unbroken, live peeps and dead peeps. The chicks were sorted and sexed accordingly into pullets and cocks. Fertility was calculated as number of fertile eggs on day 10 per number set and number fertile on day 18 per number set. Hatchability was calculated as number of chicks hatched per number set and per number transferred to the hatching machine on day 18. Means were separated using the Least Significant Difference method according to Steel and Torrie (1980)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows that two hundred and thirty seven thousand and sixty eight (237068) and ninety two thousand nine hundred and seventy three (92973) eggs were set for incubation before and after molting, respectively, of which 169988 and 55115 were hatched. There was a significant difference between production periods ($P < 0.001$) in number of eggs produced, fertility and hatchability. The fertility of eggs was significantly higher during the active laying period ($90.94 \pm 0.83\%$) than after molting ($85.50 \pm 0.77\%$). The average hatchability of the two periods per number set for incubation ($71.08 \pm 1.25\%$ and $57.55 \pm 1.02\%$, respectively) and number transferred on day 18 of incubation ($79.74 \pm 1.18\%$ and $68.31 \pm 0.85\%$, respectively), differed significantly ($P < 0.001$). In both cases, the hatchability was higher before molting than after. The observed decline in egg production, fertility and hatchability of the laying hens during the latter period, substantiates the reports in scientific literature. Alsobayel and Alkhateeb (1992) working on Saudi Arabian Baladi, hens observed higher embryonic mortality among force-molted hens compared with the control. Kemal *et al* (2003), investigating the possibility of second production in a year from rock partridges (*Alectoris graeca*) using force-molting, observed egg production, fertility, hatchability, hatchability of fertile eggs in the first and second periods to be 51.55 and 42.80 egg/hen, 83.34 and 75.73%, 66.89 and 59.80%, 80.81 and 80.22%, respectively. The researchers however found the other variables to be statistically similar between the periods, the exception being egg production ($P < 0.00$). Lower egg production was obtained post-molt, which they attributed to differences in age and seasonal conditions. Contrary to these results, Hall (1946) reported higher fertility and hatchability for White Leghorn hens molted by means of feed restriction. These differences might be attributed among other things, to breed

effect. Alodan and Mashaly (1999) compared four methods of induced molting on a commercial strain of White Leghorn and found that it significantly increased egg production from 64% to 77%. Comparing three methods of force molting in two breeds of laying chickens, Venkata *et al* (2008) reported fertility of 87.76, 89.76 and 88.04% for control, zinc oxide and feed withdrawal groups, respectively in Cornish breed. Corresponding values for Rock breed were 90.6, 91.03 and 89.87%, respectively. There was no significant difference in fertility due to different methods of molting in both breeds. In terms of hatchability, the authors reported values expressed as total egg set pooled over hatches to be 62.35, 73.59 and 75.60%, respectively, under control, zinc oxide and feed withdrawal in the Cornish layers. The corresponding values for the Rock layers were 72.65, 78.32 and 79.19%, respectively. While most of the literature encountered compared different methods of force molting, the current study only sought to determine whether force molting of an entire flock by feed restriction can simultaneously pump few more eggs out of the exhausted hens and improve fertility and hatchability, when it is deemed cheaper to recycle them, rather than immediately slaughter them after a year of relentless egg-laying.

Significant seasonal variations were also detected for all fertility and hatchability variables (Table 2). The highest fertility on day 10 ($91.80 \pm 0.36\%$) and day 18 ($89.80 \pm 0.39\%$) of incubation were observed in early wet season, followed closely by late dry season ($90.70 \pm 0.51\%$ and $88.73 \pm 0.61\%$, respectively). In terms of hatchability per number set on day 1 and number transferred on the 18th day, late dry season recorded the best performance ($73.15 \pm 1.32\%$ and $82.72 \pm 1.28\%$) ahead of the early wet season ($68.60 \pm 1.98\%$ and $75.80 \pm 2.07\%$, respectively) and the other seasons. Seasonal variations have been shown to affect fertility and hatchability (Kemal *et al.* 2003). The fact that fertility and hatchability values were higher during the late dry and early wet seasons compared with the late rainy and early dry seasons, suggests causes mediated through changes in either temperature or humidity or both, as the birds were intensively managed.

CONCLUSION

The study has shown that although egg production, fertility and hatchability in force-molted chickens decreased considerably when compared with active laying period (i.e. before molting), induced molting using feed restriction to a large extent improves these parameters in laying hens, that suffered a decline, after a year of relentless egg-laying.

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Table 1. Totals of eggs at different stages of incubation

Factor	No. set	C10	F10	T18	NH
Season					
Late dry	101844	9609	92230	90114	75279
Early wet	79920	6559	77040	72048	56856
Late wet	87516	10090	77436	76248	55800
Early dry	60740	6236	109040	53700	37160
Period					
Pre-molting	237068	20472	219596	212680	169988
Post-molting	92973	12026	81651	79407	55115

C10= number candled at day 10, F10= number fertile at day 10, T18= number transferred on day 18
NH= number hatched

Table 2. Means and standard errors of incubation sets for some fertility and hatchability indices and factors affecting them

Factor	No. set	C10	F10d	F10(%)	T18	F18(%)	H	H1(%)	H2(%)
Season	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***
Late dry	4428 ±227 ^a	417.8 ±36.2 ^a	4010 ±200 ^a	90.70 ±0.51 ^a	3918 ±195 ^a	88.73 ±0.61	3273 ±179 ^a	73.15 ±1.32 ^a	82.72 ±1.28 ^a
Early wet	3330 ±22 ^b	273.8 ±16 ^c	3210 ±272 ^b	91.80 ±0.36 ^a	3002 ±211 ^b	89.80 ±0.39	2369 ±224 ^b	68.60 ±1.98 ^b	75.80 ±2.07 ^b
Late wet	2431 ±311 ^c	280.3 ±30 ^c	2151 ±302 ^d	85.64 ±1.28 ^b	2118 ±300 ^d	84.59 ±1.37	1550 ±234 ^d	60.03 ±1.59 ^c	71.31 ±1.28 ^c
Early dry	3037 ±525 ^b	311.8 ±33.5 ^b	2726 ±494 ^c	85.84 ±1.65 ^b	2685 ±486 ^c	84.62 ±1.61	1858 ±345 ^c	57.05 ±1.86 ^d	66.84 ±1.20 ^d
period	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***
Pre-molt	4559 ±210 ^a	393.7 ±27 ^a	4223 ±208 ^a	90.94 ±0.83 ^a	4090 ±197 ^a	89.34 ±0.8 ^a	3269 ±156 ^a	71.08 ±1.25 ^a	79.74 ±1.18 ^a
Post-molt	1823 ±105 ^b	235.8 ±7.27 ^b	1601 ±106 ^b	85.50 ±0.77 ^b	1557 ±101 ^b	84.07 ±0.8 ^b	1080 ±76 ^b	57.55 ±1.02 ^b	68.30 ±0.85 ^b

Values in the same column with different superscripts are significantly different

NS=number set on day 1, H= number hatched, C10= number candled at day 10, F10= number fertile at day 10, F10= fertility at day 10, T18= number transferred on day 18, F18= fertility on day 18, H1(%) =Hatchability per number set, H2(%) = Hatchability per number transferred on day 18

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